

The effect of building information modeling on project planning, control and management

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ABSTRACT

Today, in the industries of architecture, engineering, and construction (AEC), it is essential to implement management techniques and tools, especially with increasing project scale. While the search for better techniques and tools continues, BIM building information modeling is one of the most promising developments in the industry, reflecting a digital picture of the physical and functional characteristics of a structure in order to create a reliable basis for decision making. During the life cycle of the structure and presents the project in multidimensional. Geometric data is modeled and, most importantly, project-related data such as element performance, material specifications, execution details, program, cost, etc. are also stored with the model. The BIM also incorporates many of the functions needed to model a building's life cycle, paving the way for new designs and capabilities, and changing roles and relationships between project teams. The goal is to provide a single model for all stakeholders at all stages of the project. In this paper, the main challenges in the current method of project management and control are analysed and how BIM-based project management overcomes these challenges. It explored how to use BIM to manage and gather information to build a BIM model. The benefits of planning, cost estimation, sustainability, and facilities management of BIM-based multiple-dimensional in the areas of planning, control, project management and construction were explored. At the end, a brief explanation was given about the BIM software platforms and how to work with them.

Keywords: *project planning, control and management, BIM, IFC, nD, BEP.*

1. Introduction

Building information modeling (bim) is a tool for creating and managing building data through the use of Cad and ICt tools (Nahali and Ravanshadnia, 2018). In the construction industry it has become a requirement for effective project management and control. In many developed countries of the world as a new and emerging solution to help increase accuracy, understanding and speed in the construction cycle of a building (Life Cycle) including preliminary studies, design, construction and operation and even demolition of buildings and structures It has found many applications. The United States, the United Kingdom, Finland, Denmark, Norway, Hong Kong, and Singapore have already implemented this approach in their private and public sectors (Ghomi 2016). A survey of BIM usage across North America found that 67% of engineers, 70% of architects, and 74% of contractors use BIM (Lee, G., J. Lee, et al. (2012). 2012 Business) Value of BIM in South Korea (English). SmartMarket Report. Bedford, MA, McGraw Hill Construction). Very large institutions and companies (for example, Autodesk, etc.) are implementing and expanding this method in the developed countries of the world. In different stages of a project cycle (Life Cycle) which includes preliminary studies, design of different parts (architecture, structure,

mechanical and electrical installations) due to the presence and involvement of different real and legal personalities, different construction methods and methods, materials and extensive new equipment And the variety has made this cycle more complex every day, which demands the increasing need for accuracy and the use of new and accurate methods (Khalili Qomi, 2016). On the other hand, strict standards, requirements for the design and execution of buildings in a sustainable and environmentally friendly (designGreen and Sustainable), create the need for each member of the construction team (employer to operator) to be able to get the most visual understanding and the least error in Have different stages of work. Another goal of using BIM technology is to correctly transfer the information and demands of the project owners to the design team, from the design team to the construction team, and finally from the construction team to the operator. In such a way that the initial and final goals of none of the members of the group suffer from defects and deviations (Khalili Qomi, 2016).

Figure 1: Information modeling of BIM construction projects

2. Background

The basic concepts of BIM were first introduced by Eastman in the mid-1970s with a prototype building description system. However, due to the high cost of the required hardware, its widespread use was limited until in 2002 Autodesk introduced BIM for the first time in an article. (Wikipedia and BIM Handbook, 2010). In his book *The BIM Guide*, Eastman defines it as a modeling technology and related set of processes for producing, communicating, and analyzing building models. The Pennsylvania State Research Group also defines BIM as the process of designing, analyzing, integrating, and documenting the life cycle of a building by creating a smart virtual prototype of the building using a database of information (Shakeri, Dadgar, Rashidi Nasab and Taheri Jebeli, 2017). The New York City Building Information Modeling Guide defines BIM as: Building information modeling is a technology that enables digital exchange of information and collaborative collaboration between designers by establishing digital communication between different applications, and by increasing the accuracy and integrity of designs. Significantly reduces. (Adibfar, Maghrebi, Hosseini and Bagheri, 2015). In the PMBOK definition, a project is a temporary effort to create a unique product, service or result. Project management The application of knowledge, skills, tools, and techniques related to activities / activities is done through five interrelated process groups: 1 Initial process 2 Planning process 3 Execution process 4 Monitoring and control process 5 Termination of Pmbok 2013 project And project management knowledge areas include domain management, time management, management, cost, quality management, human resource management, communications management, risk management, and logistics management and integration management. Each project in accordance with these management areas has levels of uncertainty and the main challenge is managing uncertainty and the main challenge is managing uncertainties taking into account all cases. At each stage, the project manager and other experts have tasks and many uncertainties ahead. For this reason, the use of computer-assisted systems helps professionals to perform their assigned tasks. To build a successful project management system, it is important to have access to information at the right time. This helps project experts make better decisions when needed. This information includes items such as material specifications, installation and assembly guide, product warranty services, maintenance, price information and construction and installation steps, and acts

as a common reference between the employer, the designer and the manufacturer to increase coordination, reduce errors. And waste reduces costs and increases quality (Abedini and Shakeri 2014).

3.The phases of information building modeling

The phases of the project are planning, design, implementation, operation and maintenance, which we briefly review here with the BIM approach. The planning phase in which these letters and rules are collected and the project is analyzed and feasible. Examining the concept of feasibility and design method, increasing the performance and quality of the building, better cooperation with the help of IPD are some of the pre-construction benefits for the owners. (Ebrahimi, Golabchi and Shaeafi, 2018). The most important point in contractors' use of BIM capabilities is to communicate with employers before starting construction. Integrated project delivery requires a joint collaboration agreement rather than architects; Designers and general contractors work together from the start of the project and make the best use of BIM.) (Shakeri, Dadgar, Rashidi Nasab and Taheri Jebeli 2017). The design phase includes project analysis, faster and more accurate visualization of the design, 3D model presentation, design coordination between units, automatic corrections when design changes are made, interference detection, cost estimation, energy consumption simulation, etc. .. with the help of BIM models (Ebrahimi, Golabchi and Shaeafi, 2018). Three detailed sections are divided into schematic design in which options are analyzed. Detailed design of three-dimensional models of structures, electricity and mechanics and specification of construction details, 4D planning and 5D execution cost estimation is done and horizontal for the execution stage is provided. Tender design limits the contractor's ability to apply his knowledge in the design phase, when they can have a significant impact. (Shakeri, Dadgar, Rashidi Nasab and Taheri Jebeli 2017). The construction phase includes designing the implementation method, adapting to the schedule, specifying values, managing resources, and performing planned activities. The project manager determines the optimal location for the workshop equipment by simulating the project space and the movement routes of manpower and machinery. (Qasim, Zamani Nouri and Fallahi, 2017) Advantages of construction with the help of BIM models, Adaptation of design and construction planning, better application of construction techniques, coordination of logistics with design and construction. (Ebrahimi, Golabchi and Shaeafi, 2018.). Operation and maintenance phase includes site management after project implementation, and the benefits of using BIM in this phase include improved commissioning and delivery of facility information, better facility management and performance, model integration with facility performance, and management system (Ebrahimi, Golabchi and Shaeafi 2018).

4.BIM BENEFITS

Modified information flow Because the building information pattern provides a single description of a building, you can modify and improve the information flow at any stage of a building's design, construction, and life cycle. Architects, MEPs, contractors and building owners can change or extract information to support their role at different stages of the building life cycle. A clear view of the project is obtained to improve decisions to reduce errors and improve production. Better Design Drawing The ability to predict how residents, visitors, and neighbors will react to or influence how they treat the building is an important part of the design process for architects and engineers. The ability to virtualize the HVAC system and test it virtually in a 3D environment, just as it does in a real building, can provide added assurance to the components when they start building. Advanced cost estimation Due to the depth and accuracy of the information provided by BIM, it is obvious that it can improve the accuracy of cost estimation. A simple method for extracting the amount and number of materials required can increase the speed and accuracy of the estimate and provide a better measure of the impact of design changes so that budget issues can be actively addressed. Advanced energy analysis Here, too, BIM accuracy can be simplified and help improve accuracy in energy analysis. While calculating energy use requires other software tools, the data for which such analysis is required is available in BIM (Lagüela, 2014).

Bim benefits for employers, executives, contractors, manufacturers (Taheri Borun et al., 2017).

Facilities management in the period of operation, financial forecasting and financial management, increasing the quality of projects, accurate project estimation, reducing energy consumption costs through energy optimization, increasing building efficiency	Bim benefits for employers
Investigation of pre-execution interference, better execution quality, optimization of project implementation process, safety management in execution, optimal planning and equipping of the workshop, minimum errors and mistakes and repairs in the execution stages	BIM benefits for executives
Document the project implementation stages and facilitate the process of final meetings and situations, use the designed model to build parts, identify and investigate design errors, investigate possible interferences and collisions before construction and provide solutions, material meters and cost estimates of various fronts and use in contracts	BIM Benefits for Contractors
Use of manufacturers 'products in the design and implementation stage, standard coding of manufacturers' products, complete knowledge of consumers about products before purchase	Benefits (BIM) for material producers

Table 1: Bim benefits for employers, executives, contractors, manufacturers

BIM Dimensions One of the basic and important concepts in BIM technology is building information modeling. When we talk about information dimensions, these information dimensions enter the information model, so we can produce a more complete model by adding a series of information at each stage. BIM Dimensions, like information puzzles, evolve a beam model and guide the project in achieving information integration from design to construction and operation. BIM Dimensions in each dimension or stage has its own software solutions and workflow that each stage needs special attention. (Taheri Borun ., 2017).

5.Challenges of using BIM

Ownership of Model Rights One of the primary challenges of BIM is to determine how the owner of the BIM data and information manages how to copy it (Darby, 2006). Database of Construction Objects and Components Using BIM, companies and manufacturers of construction equipment will be able to easily provide modeled product information to professionals and designers. Prevent manufacturers and manufacturers from copying their product information accurately and pass it on to others, which can lead to abuse. Lack of integrated software for full execution BIM The software used in all parts of the design, implementation and management must work seamlessly, otherwise the information in each part is generated separately and the ability to analyze and read for other parts involved in the project Will not exist. Data Entry Control It is crucial to know who and by what mechanism can provide information to the BIM model, as inaccuracies in data entry require a lengthy data review and refinement process (Darby, 2006).

6.Dimensions of building information modeling

6.1 2D Dimension Two-dimensional drawings

The first dimension in Beam technology is the 2D dimension, which is CAD or Computer Aided Design. Documents produced to date by tools such as AutoCAD can be considered as a traditional method in Beam technology. This two-dimensional method has no information and this model can not be known as a beam model. The first stage of the Beam model is a three-dimensional model that, in addition to geometry, also produces information, such as the number of walls, the length of the walls, the area or materials used. 2D Dimension is one of the details of Level 0 Beam. (Abedi Moghadam, 2016).

6.2 3D Dimension:

It is the third dimension and is the first dimension that is referred to as information dimension in Beam technology, because in this dimension, in addition to geometry, there is also information. Information is an integral part of Beam technology. (Abedi Moghadam, 2016).

Figure 2: Home design for building information modeling

6.3 4D Dimension

The fourth dimension is Time or the Time dimension. After producing the 3D model, by adding the time model, a construction simulation can be performed according to time, which helps to manage and control the project comprehensively. (Abedi Moghadam, 2016).

6.4 5D Dimension

The fifth dimension is the cost or cost dimension, in which by adding the daily price to buy materials and wages and other costs in the project, we can have the output of a price analysis. (Abedi Moghadam, 2016).

6.5 6D Dimension

The sixth dimension includes two concepts in Beam technology

- Supply of goods
- Manpower

Carbon Footprint Or the amount of emissions that are under the discussion of energy and green buildings and Sustainability or we try to produce buildings with the lowest carbon emissions. Also in this dimension it is possible to create a coordination between sustainability issues and energy analysis for optimal construction. (Abedi Moghadam, 2016).

6.6 7D Dimension

The seventh dimension is called FM or Facility Management. It means the operation and maintenance of the building, especially for projects that have general use, such as hospitals, subways, schools, universities, etc., such projects are used for years and eventually are maintained, so check this The dimension is very important. (Abedi Moghadam, 2016).The information generated in the previous six dimensions, when entered into the seventh dimension, forms a very comprehensive model that can be used as a criterion for project maintenance.

7. Software used in building information modeling

Application in sustainable development management	Application in structures	Application in architecture
Autodesk Ecotect Analysis	Autodesk Revit Structure	Autodesk Revit Architecture
Autodesk Green Building Studio	Bentley Structural Modeler	Graphisoft ArchiCad
Graphisoft EcoDesigner	Bentley RAM, STAAD and ProSteel	Nemetschek Allplan Architecture
IES Solutions Virtual Environment VE-Pro	Tekla Structures	RinhoBIM
Bentley Tas Simulator	StructureSoft Metal Wood Framing	Softtech spirit
Bentley Hevacomp	MSA Strad and Steel	CADsoft Envisioneer
Design Builder	Autodesk Robot Structural Analysis	Bentley Architecture

Table 2: Software used for building information modeling (Sotoudeh Beidakhti, 2016).

8. Bim substrates

They can be used in a variety of construction methods. Architects for modeling, design and production, engineers for structural calculation or energy management, contractors for a coordinated model, specification of construction details or facility management. Each of these platforms includes different capabilities and some of them are offered for multiple uses. Different marketing strategies lead to packages with different sets of performance, the applications and limitations of which are considered according to different types of BIM users. The choice of a software platform is based on current capabilities, future development, support network and user community that provide a collaborative environment. Most BIM design programs have interfaces with other programs for interpretation, energy analysis, cost estimation, and more. Some of them also provide opportunities for multiple users to coordinate their work with each other. BIM in most organizations includes different programs for different applications, and large companies usually support 10 to 50 different programs for the use of their employees. These platforms have enough information to support design, editing and modification, as well as parametric rules to maintain the accuracy of a building model. They may have several built-in tools for 3D modeling, estimating values, rendering, and generating maps. Here is an overview of the Revit platform from the perspective of Revit Architecture as the most widely used construction platform. (Sotoudeh Beidakhti, 2016).

9. Revit

The most famous market-leading software platform for BIM is in architectural design. Revit was introduced in 2002 by Autodesk. And a completely different context of code, with a different file structure and programming base. Revit is a family of integrated products, including Revit Architecture, Revit Structures and Revit Facilities. The program lets its users design a building and its components in 3D, interpret the model with 2D text elements, and access building information from the building model database. Revit The software is capable of 4D BIM with tools for mapping and tracking various stages in the life cycle of a building, from the initial concept to construction and then demolition. Three Revit products (architecture, structure) use RVT file extensions to store BIM models. A building is usually built using 3D objects to create walls, floors, roofs, windows, doors, electrical systems and other needed objects. These parametric objects are called three-dimensional building objects (such as doors and windows) and two-dimensional objects (such as fasteners) of the family and are stored in RFA files and entered into the RVT database when needed. In this section, Revit focuses on architectural vision. (BIM Handbook, 2010)

9.1 Revit Benefits:

- Vision as a design tool is powerful and sensitive.
- Learning to see is simple.
- Has a wide range of objects designed by software developers and manufacturers in the market.
- Due to the position of this software in the market, Revit is usually preferred when you need to exchange information with other software.
- Multi-dimensional map support in these applications, the ability to update and manage maps from different parts of the environment, such as views or schedules.

Simplicity and speed of learning, increasing the speed and accuracy of drawing as well as changing drawings, simultaneous drawing of three-dimensional and two-dimensional drawings of structural and installation drawings and simultaneous application of changes between these drawings, elimination of compliance errors with structural drawings and installations and simultaneous application Changes between these plans, elimination of errors in the adaptation of views and plans and sections, the possibility of conducting climatic studies (light and shadow) on the building, the possibility of defining construction standards in building equipment, calculating the building meter and changing it quickly if plans change, capability Communication with other BIM software through IFC as well as AtuoCAD (input and output), the possibility of volume design and its conversion into executable drawings are other benefits of this software. (BIM Handbook, 2010)

9.2 Disadvantages of Revit

This software, when working on projects with a size of more than 300 MB, is faced with a significant reduction in speed. It has limitations in the design of complex curved surfaces. (BIM Handbook, 2010)

Structural	Revit Structure (Dir), ROBOT (Dir), and RISA structural analyses (IFC), BIM ME S.A.R.L. ETABS Link, SismiCAD for FEA analysis, Graitec's Advance and ARCHE, Fastrak Building Designer, StruSoft FEM-Design, SOFTEK S-Frame, STAADPRO via SIXchange, SOFiSTiK
Mechanical	Revit MEP (Dir), HydraCAD (fire sprinklers), MagiCAD (mechanical design), QuantaCAD (mechanical laser scanning for as-builts), TOKMO (COBie facility operators handover)
Energy and environmental	Ecotect, EnergyPlus, IES all indirect, Green Building Studio via gbXML
Visualization	Mental Ray (Dir), 3ds Max (Dir), Piranasi
Facility management	Autodesk FMDesktop (Dwf), Archibus (IFC)
Site analysis	Interface with AutoCAD Civil 3D
Manufacturing components	Interface with Autodesk Inventor
Site planning	Interface with LANDCADD
Quantity takeoff for cost estimation	Interface with US Cost, Cost OS by Nomitech, Innovaya, Sage Timberline, Tocoman iLink
4D simulation	Primavera, MS Project
Scheduling and quantity takeoffs	Autodesk Navisworks
Specifications	e-SPECS, BSD SpecLink
Import models	SketchUp, AutoDesSys form, McNeel Rhinoceros, Google Earth

Table 3: sets of programs related to different work areas in Revit

Revit A powerful visual and design tool with high performance map generation tools that is user-friendly and organized and supports multitasking. This collection has a very large library of objects developed by Autodesk and third parties. Its two-way design support allows you to update and manage information from design and model

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views, and model views, including applications. Due to its dominant position in the market, this platform is more suitable for communication with other BIM tools. (BIM Handbook, 2010)

10 Conclusion

This article, while defining BIM-based projects, identified its cases and communication sections with project planning, control and management. For this purpose, the working method was stated and it was stated how the three-dimensional model was upgraded to load the required data more completely in the model and this data in the form of a creative model, how to more fully define and master the cottage project elements in planning, Establishes control, and project management. However, it should be noted that using the model will be a challenge for non-professional users. What can be explicitly said that it can be produced automatically by the model is the plan and cutting of meter meters and estimates. It also displays interventions that are notified in a timely manner prior to implementation to avoid unnecessary costs. It is expected that in the near future we will be able to benefit from all the capabilities and positive features of this technology in the construction project management departments. It is expected that by using BIM in projects, both small and large, we will be able to achieve the desired result for consultants and employers in the shortest time and at the lowest cost, which is always the case.

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